

0.1 N HCl preparation

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1. What equipment do I need to prepare 0.1 N HCl?

- You will need a volumetric flask (typically 1 L), a graduated cylinder for measuring concentrated HCl, a pipette for accurate measurement of small volumes (optional, but recommended for better precision), and DI (deionized) water.

2. What concentration of commercial hydrochloric acid should I use?

- Concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl) is typically around 37% by weight. This is much stronger than the desired 0.1 N solution. You will need to dilute it with DI water.

3. How much concentrated HCl do I need to make 1 L of 0.1 N HCl?

- You can use the following formula to calculate the volume of concentrated HCl needed:

$$\text{Volume of concentrated HCl (mL)} = \frac{(\text{Desired Normality} \times \text{Desired Volume (L)})}{(\text{Concentration of commercial HCl as a decimal})}$$

For 0.1 N HCl in 1 L:

$$\text{Volume of concentrated HCl (mL)} = \frac{(0.1 \text{ N} \times 1 \text{ L})}{(37\%)} = 2.7 \text{ mL}$$

4. Do I add water to acid or acid to water?

- Always add acid to water slowly and with stirring.** Adding water to concentrated acid can be dangerous due to the exothermic reaction (heat generation) that can cause violent splattering.

5. How do I prepare the 0.1 N HCl solution?

- Measure 2.7 mL of concentrated HCl using a graduated cylinder (for less precise measurement) or a pipette (for higher precision).
- Rinse the measuring device with a small amount of DI water and add the rinse water to the volumetric flask.
- Add approximately 500 mL of DI water to the volumetric flask.
- Slowly add the measured concentrated HCl to the flask while swirling gently.

5. Rinse the measuring device again with DI water and add the rinse water to the flask.
6. Fill the volumetric flask to the mark with DI water. Swirl the solution thoroughly to ensure proper mixing.

6. What safety precautions should I take when preparing 0.1 N HCl?

- Wear gloves, safety glasses or a face shield, and a lab coat.
- Work in a well-ventilated fume hood.
- Be aware of the proper disposal procedures for waste HCl according to your institution's guidelines.

7. How can I check the accuracy of the prepared 0.1 N HCl solution?

- This is typically done in a more advanced laboratory setting by performing a standardization process using a primary standard solution. However, for many routine applications, the dilution calculation is sufficient.

8. Can I store the prepared 0.1 N HCl solution?

- Yes, you can store diluted HCl in a properly labeled container made of a suitable material (e.g., glass or polyethylene) in a cool, dry place. Over time, the concentration of HCl may slightly decrease due to evaporation. It's recommended to label the bottle with the preparation date and expected shelf life.